

**AI IN MEDICINE: WHERE ARE WE NOW AND WHERE ARE WE
GOING?**

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Abstract: Advancements in AI enable personalizing healthcare, for example by investigating disease origins at the genetic or molecular level, understanding intraindividual drug effects, and fusing multi-modal personal physiological, behavioral, laboratory, and clinical data to uncover pathophysiology new aspects of. Future efforts should address equity, fairness, explainability, and generalizability of AI models.

Keywords: Personalized medicine, ML and AI algorithms, big data, DL(deep learning), individualized healthcare.

Introduction

Personalized medicine is a novel approach to understanding health, disease, and treatment outcomes based on personal data, including medical diagnoses, clinical phenotype, laboratory studies, imaging, environmental, demographic, and lifestyle factors. Precision medicine often overlaps with this concept and also includes utilizing genomic data to tailor a plan of treatment or prevention of a particular disease. Personalized and precision medicine promise a better understanding of health and medicine, improvements in the early detection of diseases, and better long-term health and chronic disease management.

The multi-modal information originating from multiple domains can be collected from individuals because of recent advancements in sensing, cloud infrastructure, medicine, genetics, metabolomics, and imaging technologies, among others. However, with such innovations in sensing and diagnostic testing capabilities, an incredible amount of personal data can now be generated for each patient. Appropriately storing and analyzing this voluminous personal data can be a challenging and daunting task.

Thankfully, advances are also being made in these directions to increase the capabilities and efficiency with which we can digitize, store, and analyze these large volumes of personal and population-level data. Ultimately, the combined advancements in biomolecular, imaging, and sensing technologies, along with

hardware, software, and data science, and the ability of the medical community to leverage these technologies effectively, have together enabled personalized/precision medicine.

Personalized/precision medicine

Through these emerging technologies and integration of the data generated by them, the promise of a truly “multi-omics” approach to research and medicine is increasingly being realized. Examples of the multi-omics approach in practice include:

(1) gut microbiome relationships to health and disease, as mediated and characterized by the human metabolome and microbial meta-omes (i.e., metage-nome, metatranscriptome, and meta-metabolome)

(2) applications of machine learning to large multi-modal multi-omic datasets to uncover new relationships, and

(3) variations on sequencing-based technologies to uncover higher-order information, including epigenetics and chromatin configuration (e.g., ATAC-Seq, RRBS, Hi-C).

Further, a new appreciation for the key role of drug-metabolizing genes has come to light. Specifically, a host of genes in the Cyp (Cytochrome P450) family have been found to control the metabolism of a vast array of drugs, which in turn enables a precision approach to drug dosing on an individualized level. Applying these approaches complementarily will be key to a more comprehensive assessment of the biomolecular milieu.

Figure 1. Pipeline of data analysis in healthcare using artificial intelligence

Multi-modal personal “big data” are curated from diversified sources and integrated with electronic health records that are analyzed using artificial intelligence, more specifically machine learning or deep learning algorithms (e.g., supervised, semi-supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning).

AI and ML in personalized/precision medicine

AI/ML models have been successfully applied to a wide variety of genomics data, particularly in cases with high dimensional and complex data that are challenging to process using traditional statistical methods. Genome-wide association studies, which involve rapidly scanning markers across the genomes of thousands or more people to discover genetic variants associated with a particular disease, have benefitted substantially from ML. One example is in Type 1 diabetes, where there is an improved

risk assessment using ML algorithms that can account for interactions between a large collection of biomarkers.

Using treatment outcomes data generated from previous patients treated for a disease, ML models can identify which future patients may benefit from a specific treatment based on their characteristics. An example of this is genetically informed therapeutic planning (using support vector machine-based anti-cancer drug sensitivity prediction method using genomic data) for patients with pharmaco-genomically actionable variants, where titrated prescription and dosing are critical. This advancement can avoid unnecessary treatments in non-responders and support titrated prescription and dosing to maximize the anti-cancer effect in responders.

Figure 2. Overview of incorporation of artificial intelligence into precision medicine.

The incorporation of artificial intelligence into precision medicine has demonstrated tremendous potential and progress in personalized care, clinical decision support systems, early disease detection, and tracking disease progression. However, there are technical and ethical challenges (e.g., fairness and bias, transparency and liability, trust, safety, and security) that may hinder the progress and reliability of the field and delay clinical implementation.

Overall, the current value and future potential of AI in personalized health care, early detection of disease, tracking disease progression, and as a clinical decision support tool have been amply demonstrated (Figure 2). AI-assisted precision medicine has demonstrated promise not only for personalization of therapies for existing diseases, but also for individual risk prediction and personalized prevention plans.

Challenges and considerations.

Although tremendous progress has been made using AI techniques and high-volume data, there is substantial room for improvement. While the potential of AI/ ML in personalized/precision medicine is clear, there are many remaining concerns and challenges, both technical and ethical, that may hinder progress and reliability of the field and delay clinical implementation. Some examples of this are:

(1) Fairness and bias: Data and algorithms can reflect, reinforce, and perpetuate biases. When the data utilized to train AI is either incomplete (e.g., lack of representation from underserved and underrepresented communities) or inherently biased (e.g., collected in settings where existing stereotypes affect the data itself), the models built will be problematic and can serve to further exacerbate disparities and biases.

(2) Limited data availability: In recent years, DL models have become increasingly popular, achieving great performance in many areas of biomedical applications. However, due to their data-hungry nature, DL models cannot easily learn

from small datasets, and available datasets are often insufficient in size to train deep learning models.

(3) Data deluge: As a society we are generating ever more data both in and out of clinical settings, with healthcare data storage projected to exceed 2,000 exabytes by 2020.10 Collecting such multimodal data on a large scale opens new data storage and organization challenges and costs.

(4) Transparency and liability: DL and other high complexity ML models may demonstrate greater accuracy than simpler models, but are opaque and do not provide users with insights as to how the algorithm arrives at its conclusions. This ‘‘black box’’ nature of the technology is particularly concerning in healthcare where lives are on the line. Additionally, where the responsibility for AI-assisted medical decisions lies is not always clear. (

5) Data drift: A common assumption in AI (particularly ML) algorithms is that data from the past (used for the model training) is a representation of the data from the future (for which the model will eventually be deployed). Unfortunately, this is rarely the case in real-world settings and so changes in the data may affect the model’s behavior and accuracy in a real-world deployment.

(6) Data safety and privacy: AI algorithms use significant amounts of personal data for their decision making. However, software and corresponding hardware may have security flaws which can lead to theft of personal and health information.

(7) Trust: Similar to other technologies, early mistakes and failures in technologies can lead to general mistrust which can reduce adoption and utilization of the technology.

Conclusions

Technological advancements in sensor hardware and AI algorithms equipped with personalized/precision medicine have already resulted in an unprecedented acceleration of personalized therapy, early disease detection, and personalized disease prevention strategies.

Overall, the synergy between AI and personalized/precision medicine could ultimately decrease the disease burden for the public at large, and therefore, the cost of preventable health care for all. However, we should remain vigilant with an ethics and equity lens to ensure that these advancements are not increasing health-related disparities and exacerbating existing inequities or creating new divides in care or health-related outcomes.

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